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LONG-TERM RESULTS OF TREATMENT OF COMPLETE TRAUMATIC DISLOCATION OF PERMANENT TEETH IN CHILDREN

Abstract.

Complete tooth dislocation (traumatic extraction, avulsion, luxation, disarticulation) is one of the types of acute dental trauma, characterized by the loss of a tooth from the alveolus under the influence of a strong blow.

Key words: *immediate or delayed replantation, tooth dislocation.*

According to Korsak A.K. (2002), traumatic complete dislocation in children accounts for 10.6% of traumatic injuries to temporary teeth and 6.9% of injuries to permanent teeth [3]. In childhood, the anterior teeth of the upper jaw (central and lateral incisors) are dislocated mainly, and the teeth of the lower jaw are dislocated much less frequently [3, 7]. The absence of one or more anterior permanent teeth in the dental arch leads to displacement of adjacent teeth and antagonist teeth, shortening and narrowing of the dentition, causes swallowing disorders, contributes to the formation of an open bite, is an aesthetic disadvantage and leads to phonetic disorders [7, 8]. In this regard, the question of treatment tactics for complete traumatic dislocation and the possible preservation of dislocated teeth is relevant. In patients under the age of 15 years, preservation of the anterior teeth seems to be especially important, since there is no satisfactory treatment alternative until the end of jaw growth [9]. The method of choice in the treatment of complete traumatic dislocation of permanent teeth is immediate or delayed replantation (returning the tooth to its alveolus). Currently, this method is used quite often and is widely described in the literature [1, 2, 4–9]. However, the opinions of the authors are contradictory: some of them consider replantation to be unpromising, since the service life of a replanted tooth is on average up to five years, while others provide observations of the functional activity of such teeth for more than 10 years [5]. The success of the replantation operation depends on many factors: 1 the time the dislocated tooth remains outside the oral cavity; storage environment and proper transportation to a medical facility; preservation of the periodontal ligament around the dislocated tooth; the degree of damage to the tooth itself and the bone walls of the alveoli; stages of root formation; method of intraoral fixation; adequate antibiotic therapy in combination with physiotherapeutic measures; subsequent dynamic monitoring of the patient for the purpose of timely diagnosis and treatment of complications. The purpose of this study is to analyze the incidence of complete traumatic dislocation of permanent teeth in children depending on gender, age, group of the tooth and to study the long-term results of

replantation of dislocated teeth. Materials and methods. We analyzed the archival material of the health care facility “4th Children's City Clinical Hospital” for the period from 2002 to 2006, inclusive. Among 836 children aged from 6 months to 18 years who sought specialized dental care with traumatic injuries of the maxillofacial area, 36 children had complete traumatic dislocation of 42 permanent teeth. 28 patients had 31 permanent teeth replanted. We studied the medical histories of these 28 children. At the Republican Clinical Dental Clinic of Minsk, 18 patients were examined after replantation of dislocated permanent teeth, including 6 children examined after 4–5 years, 6 children aged 3.5–2 years, and 6 children examined after 6 months–1 year. To assess the long-term results of replantation, the following clinical criteria were used: 1. Safety of the replanted tooth in the socket. 2. Tooth stability. 3. The position of the tooth in relation to neighboring teeth and antagonist teeth. 4. Crown color. 5. Pain on percussion. 6. Condition of the oral mucosa in the area of the replanted tooth. All patients underwent an X-ray examination of the replanted teeth to determine: 1 The type of engraftment (fusion) of the tooth. 1 Presence of inflammatory changes in the root apex area. 1 Root states. Results and discussion. Our analysis of the dynamics of referral of children with complete traumatic dislocation of permanent teeth in the health care facility “4th Children's City Clinical Hospital” for the period from 2002 to 2006, revealed that children with complete traumatic dislocation of permanent teeth account for an average of $4.35 \pm 0.71\%$ of the number of those who applied with traumatic injuries to the maxillofacial area. The data is presented in Fig. 1. We also analyzed the dynamics of the incidence of complete traumatic dislocation in relation to other acute traumatic injuries of permanent teeth (Fig. 2). As a result of the study, it was established that complete traumatic dislocation accounts for $19.41 \pm 2.97\%$ of all traumatic injuries to the hard tissues of permanent teeth in children who sought help at the 4th Children's City Clinical Hospital. In addition, a trend towards an increase in the number of dislocated permanent teeth in children was revealed during the ob-

ervation period. It was found that dislocations of permanent teeth occur 2 times more often in boys than in girls ($67.86 \pm 7.78\%$ and $32.14 \pm 7.78\%$, respectively). Moreover, at the age of 6–11 years it is 2.5 times more common than among adolescents 12–18 years old. When analyzing the group affiliation of teeth with complete dislocation, it was revealed that damage to teeth on the upper jaw is observed 9 times more often (38 teeth or $90.31 \pm 4.56\%$) than on the lower jaw (4 teeth or $9.69 \pm 4.56\%$). Moreover, complete dislocation of permanent upper central incisors occurs 6 times more often than upper lateral incisors ($77.41 \pm 6.45\%$ and $12.9 \pm 5.17\%$, respectively). In the lower jaw, the same trend remains: the central incisors are more often injured ($6.45 \pm 3.79\%$), less often the lateral incisors ($3.24 \pm 2.73\%$). Analysis of the causes of complete traumatic dislocation in children based on anamnestic data revealed that the most common cause of this pathology is the so-called “school” injury (fights, games), which amounts to $39.29 \pm 9.40\%$; Injuries as a result of a road traffic accident ($14.29 \pm 6.74\%$), downhill skiing ($10.71 \pm 5.95\%$) and other causes ($17.86 \pm 7.37\%$) were less common. In $17.86 \pm 7.37\%$ of cases, the cause could not be determined due to lack of data in the medical records. We have studied the timing of replantation, i.e. the time period from the moment of injury to the replantation operation. As a result of the study, it was found that only 6 patients ($21.43 \pm 7.99\%$) underwent replantation within the first 2 hours after injury, 11 ($39.29 \pm 9.40\%$) - within the first 24 hours, 6 ($21.43 \pm 7.99\%$) - in a period of time from 24 to 72 hours, one patient ($3.57 \pm 3.57\%$) - more than 72 hours later and not specified. The patients were in hospital for 1 to 13 days, which the average was 7.1 bed days. Examination of children long after replantation revealed that in 5 patients out of 18 examined ($27.78 \pm 10.86\%$), the replanted tooth in the socket was missing due to repeated trauma or root resorption (Fig. 3). Of these, three children lost their avulsed teeth within 1 year after replantation, and two - after 3 years. Dental defects in the area of dislocated teeth were replaced with a partial removable plate denture in 4 children out of 18 examined ($22.22 \pm 10.08\%$) (Fig. 4, 5); in 1 patient ($5.55 \pm 5.55\%$) such a defect was replaced with a fixed structure - a metal-ceramic bridge. We found that in 12 children, the replanted teeth were stable, and only one child ($7.69 \pm 7.69\%$) had significant mobility due to root resorption (Fig. 6, 7). In 3 out of 13 children ($23.08 \pm 12.16\%$), the replanted teeth were changed in color. Percussion of all replanted teeth was painless. The mucous membrane in the area of the replanted teeth is without pathological changes. When assessing the position of the replanted tooth in the dentition, it was found that normal variants were observed in 5 out of 13 children ($38.46 \pm 14.04\%$) (Fig. 8); supraocclusion was noted in 6 children ($46.15 \pm 14.39\%$) (Fig. 9); 1 child

($7.69 \pm 7.69\%$) had infraocclusion (Fig. 10), medial inclination of the replanted tooth - 1 patient ($7.69 \pm 7.69\%$). It was found that 9 out of 18 patients ($50.0 \pm 12.13\%$) need orthodontic treatment, but only 7 people ($38.89 \pm 11.82\%$) are being treated by an orthodontist. As a result of the analysis of intraoral radiographs, it was revealed that the periodontal type of engraftment of the replanted tooth (syndesmosis) was observed in 3 children out of 13 ($23.08 \pm 12.16\%$) (Fig. 11), bone (synostosis, ankylosis) - in 2 patients ($15.38 \pm 10.44\%$) (Fig. 12), mixed (periodontal-fibrous-osseous) - have 5 children ($38.46 \pm 14.04\%$) (Fig. 13). One child ($7.69 \pm 7.69\%$) had inflammation at the apex of the root of the replanted tooth, inflammatory root resorption was observed in 2 children ($15.38 \pm 10.44\%$). Thus, replantation of permanent teeth as a method of treating complete traumatic dislocation is, on the one hand, quite effective; This is an organ-preserving operation that prevents bone tissue atrophy, displacement of adjacent teeth, and also eliminates cosmetic defects in the dentition. On the other hand, in childhood, replantation of permanent teeth is a temporary method of therapy, since children, compared to adults, have a higher activity of bone growth factors, which subsequently causes ankylosis or root resorption of the replanted teeth.

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